

Concentration

HCB

Σ DDTs

Σ PCBs

Hg

Annular seabream
Atlantic horse mackerel
Comber
Common pandora
Common two-banded seabream
Four-spot megrim
Mediterranean rainbow wrasse
Painted comber
Pearly razorfish
Small-spotted catshark
White seabream
Angler
Common dentex
Common dolphinfish
Conger
Dusky grouper
European hake
Greater amberjack
John Dory
Mediterranean moray
Red scorpionfish

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